

photonics

certificate

bachelors

doctoral

Directory

masters

UK

Optical photonics formations

2015 / 2016

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

introduction

Where to study Photonics? If you are interested in training to work in this innovative and challenging sector, you will find in this new directory all the optics training courses offered by universities and schools in UK.

This directory is your tool. Whether you are a young or advanced student and interested in developing or improving your skills in optics, you will find the answers to help guide you through the options and direct your career path.

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NVQ

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A LEVEL

CERTIFICATE

FOUNDATION YEAR

NVQ

Engineering

This NVQ qualification may be taken with no qualifications, or at higher levels depending on qualifications. This will provide a stepping stone into engineering and manufacturing, which could lead to a career in a photonics industry.

Contact : <http://www.cityandguilds.com/qualifications-and-apprenticeships/engineering/mechanical/2850-engineering#tab=information>

Apprenticeship

Fianium

Southampton, South East

Fianium is a fiber laser company focused on ultra-fast, high power laser systems. They are currently researching apprenticeships for those with a passion for photonics, but without formal qualifications.

Contact : careers@fianium.com

<http://fianium.com/careers.htm>

A Level

Physics

An A level in physics usually includes topics such as Optics, the fundamentals of Quantum Physics, Waves and sometimes lasers. is the normal route towards a degree or career in photonics.

Mathematics

A Mathematics A level is usually required for further study of physics and photonics in higher education.

Certificate

Physics and Mathematics

Brkbeck University of London

London, Greater London

This intensive course will prepare you for physics, mathematics, engineering and computer science degrees. There are no formal entry requirements. The course contains the basics of physics and maths, and contains an introduction to optics, waves and quantum effects.

Contact : +44 (0)20 7631 6000

http://www.bbk.ac.uk/study/2016/undergraduate/programmes/UCHPHYMA_C/

Certificate in Physics The Open University

Distance learning

This course has no formal entry requirements, and provides a good basic foundation in physics. The course teaches the fundamentals of Quantum Physics. This course can act as a stepping stone into further study or experience in photonics.

Contact : 0300 303 5303 – general-enquiries@open.ac.uk
<http://www.open.ac.uk/courses/qualifications/s20#careers>

Foundation year in Engineering/Physics/Maths and English Language CertHE University of Dundee

Dundee, Scotland

Throughout the degree guest lectures are given from a variety of speakers to help you appreciate how Engineering, Physics & Maths issues are handled in the real world. This course will raise English language ability, enhance academic skills for university study and help students adapt to future Engineering, Physics and Maths in university.

Contact : +44 (0)1382 38 38 38 – SSE@dundee.ac.uk
<http://www.dundee.ac.uk/study/ug/foundation-year-epm-english-language/#!info-why-dundee>

Foundation year

Physics with Foundation Year Aberystwyth University

Aberystwyth, Wales

Available to candidates without formal qualifications who have suitable background education, experience and motivation.

Contact : Dr. Balazs Pinter – 01970 628624 – phys-admissions@aber.ac.uk
<https://courses.aber.ac.uk/undergraduate/physics-degree-with-foundation-year/>

Physics and Astronomy (Gateway) University of St Andrews

Fife, Scotland

Physics & Astronomy (Gateway) is an alternative entry route to the University of St Andrews' degree programmes offered by the School of Physics & Astronomy. The programme is aimed at Scottish students who may not have been able to obtain the grades usually required by the School due to their circumstances or educational background.

Contact : +44 (0)1334 46 2150 – physics@st-andrews.ac.uk
<https://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/study/ug/options/routes/physics-gateway/>

Physics with a Preliminary Year of Study University of Bristol

Bristol, South West

For students without standard entry qualifications for a degree course in Physics.

Contact : +44 (0)117 928 8153 – sci-ug-admissions@bristol.ac.uk

<http://www.bristol.ac.uk/physics/courses/undergraduate/>

Physics with Foundation Durham University

Durham, North East

For students without standard entry qualifications for a degree course in Physics.

Contact : +44 (0)191 334 0172 – foundation.centre@durham.ac.uk

<https://www.dur.ac.uk/courses/info/?id=7012&title=Physics+with+Foundation&code=F302&type=BSC&year=2015#coursecontent>

Physics with a Foundation Year University of Hull

Hull, Midlands

For students without standard entry qualifications for a degree course in Physics.

Contact : 01482 465501 – admissions-physics@hull.ac.uk

<http://www2.hull.ac.uk/science/physics.aspx>

Physics with Science Foundation Year Keele University

Staffordshire, West Midlands

For students without standard entry qualifications for a degree course in Physics.

Contact : Professor Peter Haycock – 01782 734478 – foundationyear@keele.ac.uk

<http://www.keele.ac.uk/foundationcourses/sciencefoundationyear/#tabs-1>

Physics with a Foundation Year University of Kent

Canterbury, South East

Quantum Physics, Relativity Optics, Optics and Light may be studied as in a standard physics course albeit a year later due to having to take the foundation year.

Contact : +44 (0)1227 827272 – information@kent.ac.uk

<http://www.kent.ac.uk/courses/undergraduate/24/physics-with-a-foundation-year>

Physics with a Foundation Year Leicester University

Leicester, East Midlands

Light, Optics and the Quantum World' is one of the core modules taken in this course.

Contact : Dr Paul Howes – 0116 252 3587 – Paul.Howes@leicester.ac.uk

<http://www2.le.ac.uk/study/ugp/physics/foundation>

Science and Engineering Foundation Studies *Loughborough University*

Loughborough, Central UK

This programme helps students who want to study a science or engineering degree at Loughborough, but who have arrived at this decision via an unconventional route.

Contact : 01509 223 343 – Physics@lboro.ac.uk

<http://www.lboro.ac.uk/departments/physics/>

Applied Physics *The Manchester Metropolitan University*

Manchester, North West

This degree is suitable for students who wish to study physics both at a fundamental, theoretical level and across all its broad and varied real world applications.

Contact : +44 (0)161 247 1779 – se.courses@mmu.ac.uk

<http://www2.mmu.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/2016/13252/>

Physics with a Foundation Year in Science *University of Nottingham*

Nottingham, East Midlands

The programme is designed for UK and EU students whose qualifications do not meet the current admissions requirements for direct entry to undergraduate degree programmes in engineering and the physical sciences. We encourage a range of high-level applicants from a wide range of backgrounds.

Contact : 0115 951 5165 – julie.kenney@nottingham.ac.uk

<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/physics/index.aspx>

University Foundation Degree Year in Physics *Nottingham Trent University*

Nottingham, East Midlands

Study the Quantum World and Optics at the Nottingham Trent University. There will be an extra foundation year if you choose to take this course.

Contact : +44 (0)115 848 4200 – applications@ntu.ac.uk

[http://www.ntu.ac.uk/apps/pss/course_finder/118277-1/39/bsc_\(hons\)_physics.aspx?yoe=6&st=1&s=1&sv=PHYS&sl=1|2#course](http://www.ntu.ac.uk/apps/pss/course_finder/118277-1/39/bsc_(hons)_physics.aspx?yoe=6&st=1&s=1&sv=PHYS&sl=1|2#course)

Physics with a Foundation Year *University of Sheffield*

Sheffield, North East

If you don't have the usual scientific or mathematical background for our degrees, a foundation year is for you. Your first year will be spent improving your knowledge and skills, so you're at the right level to move to a degree.

Contact : 0114 222 4362 – physics.ucas@sheffield.ac.uk

<https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/prospectus/courseDetails.do?id=F3092016>

Physics with a Foundation Year University of Southampton

Southampton, South West

The Foundation Year provides an introduction to mathematics, mechanics, computer programming, electricity & electronics and engineering principles and provides the skills required to study successfully for an undergraduate degree.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 3113 – foundationyr@soton.ac.uk

<http://www.phys.soton.ac.uk/programmes/f301-bscmphys-physics-foundation-year>

Physics and Astronomy (with a Foundation Year) University of Sussex

Brighton, South East

An increasing number of students are keen to study for a degree in physics or astrophysics but – although they have the necessary talent – their qualifications do not include the required Physics and Mathematics A levels (or their equivalent). This course is designed to address this, and includes a specially designed foundation year taught at Sussex.

Contact : +44 (0)1273 678416 – ug.enquiries@sussex.ac.uk

<http://www.sussex.ac.uk/study/ug/2015/1563/31103>

Physics incorporating a Foundation Year Swansea University

Swansea, Wales

The Department of Physics offers a 4-year Physics with Integrated Foundation Year Degree scheme (F301) which is appropriate for students who are yet to achieve the necessary skills in physics and mathematics.

Contact : 01792 295720 – physics-admissions@swansea.ac.uk

<http://www.swansea.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/science/physics/bsc-physics-with-foundation-year-f301/>

Physics with Foundation Year University of York

York, North East

The Foundation Year course offers an opportunity for those who have potential, but who do not possess appropriate qualifications, to develop the skills needed to progress to completing one of our degree programmes.

Contact : Dr. Erik Wagenaars – +44 (0)1904 322241 – physics-admissions@york.ac.uk

<https://www.york.ac.uk/physics/undergraduate/degree-courses/bsc-physics-foundation/>

BACHELORS

Physics

University of Aberdeen

Aberdeen, Scotland

Light Science and Practical Optics & Electronics is a compulsory 2nd year course.

Contact : +44 (0) 1224 273504 – sras@abdn.ac.uk

<http://www.abdn.ac.uk/study/courses/undergraduate/F300/>

Physical Sciences

University of Aberdeen

Aberdeen, Scotland

Light Science and Practical Optics & Electronics is a compulsory 2nd year course.

Contact : +44 (0) 1224 273504 – sras@abdn.ac.uk

<http://www.abdn.ac.uk/study/courses/undergraduate/F302/>

Physics

Aberystwyth University

Aberystwyth, Wales

Optics is a compulsory 2nd year course, while optronics is a compulsory 3rd year course.

Contact : Dr. Balazs Pinter – +44 (0) 1970 628624 – phys-admissions@aber.ac.uk

<https://courses.aber.ac.uk/undergraduate/bsc-physics-degree/>

Applied Physics

Aston University

Aston, West Midlands

A and 2 Bs minimum of maths and Physics. Commercial and industrial applications of Physics.

Contact : Dr Sonia Boscolo – +44(0)121 204 3495 – s.a.boscolo@aston.ac.uk

www.aston.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/school/eas/bsc-applied-Physics/

Physics

University of Bath

Bath, Southwest England

Optics is a compulsory 2nd year course, while optronics is a compulsory 3rd year course.

Contact : Dr. Balazs Pinter – +44 (0) 1970 628624 – phys-admissions@aber.ac.uk

<https://courses.aber.ac.uk/undergraduate/bsc-physics-degree/>

Physics

Queen's University Belfast

Belfast, Ireland

Optics, Lasers, Quantum Mechanics and Optoelectronics will be covered by the course.

Contact : +44 (0) 28 9097 3838 – admissions@qub.ac.uk

<http://www.qub.ac.uk/home/StudyatQueens/CourseFinder/UG/Physics/F303/>

Physics

The University of Birmingham

Birmingham, West Midlands

Optics, Waves and Quantum Mechanics taught in first year. Optional Optics in 2nd year.

Contact : +44(0)121 414 4563 – Physics-adms@bham.ac.uk

<http://www.birmingham.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/Physics/Physics-bsc.aspx>

Applied Physics

The University of Bradford

Bradford, Yorkshire and the Humber

One core module is the Optics, Waves and Oscillations module.

Contact : +44 (0) 800 073 1225 – admissions-eng-inf@bradford.ac.uk

<http://www.bradford.ac.uk/study/courses/view/?c=applied-Physics-bsc-3-years>

Physics

University of Bristol

Bristol, Southwest England

Modern Optics in year 3.

Contact : +44 (0)117 394 1639 – sci-ug-admissions@bristol.ac.uk

www.bristol.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/2016/Physics/bsc-Physics/

Mathematics with Physics

University of Cambridge

Cambridge, East of England

Choice of Quantum Mechanics in year 2. No other links to Photonics.

Contact : +44(0) 122 376 6879 – admissions@maths.cam.ac.uk

<http://www.undergraduate.study.cam.ac.uk/courses/mathematics>

Natural Sciences

University of Cambridge

Cambridge, East of England

Optics and Quantum Mechanics is offered in the first year, Quantum Mechanics in 2nd

year, In the 3rd and 4th years, Quantum condensed matter Physics and advanced

Quantum theory

Contact : +44 (0) 122 376 6879 – admissions@maths.cam.ac.uk

<http://www.undergraduate.study.cam.ac.uk/courses/mathematics>

Physics

Cardiff University

Cardiff, Wales

Optics is a compulsory module in the 2nd year, while laser physics and non-linear physics is an optional module in the 3rd year.

Contact : Dr Chris North – + 44 (0) 292 087 0537 – Admissions@astro.cf.ac.uk

<http://courses.cardiff.ac.uk/undergraduate/course/detail/F300.html>

Natural Sciences University of Chester

Chester, North West England

Quantum Physics in year 1 with Quantum Mechanics in year 2.

Contact : +44 (0) 124 451 1000 – enquiries@chester.ac.uk

<http://www.chester.ac.uk/undergraduate/natural-sciences>

Physics with Materials Science University of Chester

Chester, North West England

Quantum Physics in year 1 with Quantum Mechanics in year 2.

Contact : Graham Smith – +44 (0) 124 451 1000 – enquiries@chester.ac.uk

<http://chester.ac.uk/undergraduate/Physics-materials-science>

Physics University College Cork

Cork, Republic of Ireland

Quantum Physics is a module in the 2nd year while Quantum Mechanics is in the 3rd year. Optics is an optional module in the 3rd year

Contact : Prof John McInerney – +353 (0)21 490 2468 – j.mcinerney@ucc.ie

<http://www.physics.ucc.ie/>

Applied Physics and Instrumentation Cork Institute of Technology

Cork, Republic of Ireland

Applied optics is a course in the 2nd year.

Contact : Richard Peard – +44(0)021 4335870 – richard.peard@cit.ie

<http://www.cit.ie/course/CR001>

Environmental Science & Sustainable Technology Cork Institute of Technology

Cork, Republic of Ireland

Applied optics is a course in the 2nd year.

Contact : Eamonn Butler – +44 (0) 021 433 5870 – eamonn.butler@cit.ie

<http://www.cit.ie/course/CR365>

Applied Mathematics and Theoretical Science Coventry University

Coventry, West Midlands

Quantum Physics in the second year.

Contact : +44 (0) 24 7765 2222 – studentenquiries@coventry.ac.uk

<http://www.coventry.ac.uk/course-structure/2015/faculty-of-engineering-and-computing/undergraduate/applied-mathematics-and-theoretical-Physics-bsc-hons/?theme=main>

Mathematics and Physics

De Monfort University

Coventry, West Midlands

Quantum Physics in the second year.

Contact : +44 (0) 24 7765 2222 – studentenquiries@coventry.ac.uk

<http://www.coventry.ac.uk/course-structure/engineering-and-computing/undergraduate-degree/2016-17/mathematics-and-Physics-bsc-hons/?theme=main>

Physics

The University of Bradford

Leicester, East Midlands

Optics and Quantum Physics are course modules.

Contact : +44 (0)116 2 50 60 70

<http://www.dmu.ac.uk/study/courses/undergraduate-courses/Physics-bsc-hons.aspx>

Applied Physics

Dublin City University

Dublin, Republic of Ireland

Light and Optics is a 1st year course available, Quantum physics is a 2nd year course, while Quantum mechanics is taught in year 3. There is a wave optics module in year 3.

Contact : Dr Tony Cafolla – 353 170 05332 – tony.cafolla@dcu.ie

<https://www.dcu.ie/prospective/deginfo.php?classname=AP>

Physics

University College Dublin

Dublin, Republic of Ireland

Fields, waves and light is a first year module, electromagnetism and optics and introductory quantum mechanics are taught in year 2. Quantum mechanics, Optics and Lasers and applied optics are taught in year 3.

Contact : Emma Sokell – 35317167777 – emma.sokell@ucd.ie

<http://www.ucd.ie/physics/undergraduatestudents/dn200physics/>

Science with Nanotechnology

Dublin Institute of Technology

Dublin, Republic of Ireland

Optics, Lasers and Quantum physics are taught in the third year.

Contact : Dr. Gordon Chambers – 01 402 2856 – gordon.chambers@dit.ie

<http://www.dit.ie/study/undergraduate/programmes/dt227/>

Physics with Energy & Environment

Dublin Institute of Technology

Dublin, Republic of Ireland

Optics and Quantum mechanics are taught in the second year, Optics, Electromagnetism and Lasers are offered along with Quantum Physics in the third year.

Contact : Dr John Doran – 01 402 4953 – john.doran@dit.ie

<http://www.dit.ie/study/undergraduate/programmes/dt221/>

Physics Technology Dublin Institute of Technology

Dublin, Republic of Ireland

Optics and Quantum Mechanics are courses taught in the second year. Optics, Electromagnetism & Lasers and Quantum Physics are taught in the third year. Lasers & Optical communications, Applied Optical Spectroscopy & Advanced Optics are taught in the fourth year.

Contact : Siobhan Daly – 01 402 4927 – siobhan.daly@dit.ie
<http://www.dit.ie/study/undergraduate/programmes/dt222/>

Physics University of Dundee

Dundee, Scotland

You will study Light, Waves, Optics, Quantum Mechanics and Quantum properties of matter. There are advanced Quantum Mechanics, Photonics and Optics if you take a masters degree.

Contact : Graham Smith – +44 (0)1382 38 38 38 – SSE@dundee.ac.uk
<http://www.dundee.ac.uk/study/ug/physics/>

Electronic Engineering and Physics University of Dundee

Dundee, Scotland

This course is a variation of the Physics bachelors, which includes the study of Light, Waves, Optics, Quantum Mechanics and Quantum properties of matter along with electronic engineering modules.

Contact : Prof John McInerney – +44 (0)1382 38 38 38 – SSE@dundee.ac.uk
<http://www.dundee.ac.uk/study/ug/physics/>

Physics Durham University

Durham, North East

Quantum theory is a core module in year 3.

Contact : +44 (0)191 334 3726 – Physics.admissions@durham.ac.uk
<https://www.dur.ac.uk/courses/info/?id=7002&title=Physics&code=F300&type=BSC&year=2015>

Chemical Physics University of East Anglia

Norwich, East of England

Quantum Mechanics in first year with Modern Chemical Physics, such as Laser Interactions, in the third year.

Contact : 01603 591515 – admissions@uea.ac.uk
http://www.uea.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/degree/detail/bsc-chemical-Physics?utm_campaign=web_listing_UCAS&utm_source=SCI_CHE_UG&utm_medium=listing&utm_content=BSc_Chemical_Physics

Physics

University of Edinburgh

Edinburgh, Scotland

Quantum Physics is offered in years 2 and 3, with advanced quantum modules available throughout the degree and particularly in years 3 and 4. A Lasers & Optics module is offered in the fourth year.

Contact : *Caroline Keir – +44 (0) 131 651 7855 – enquiries@ph.ed.ac.uk*

http://www.ed.ac.uk/studying/undergraduate/degrees?id=0,4&cw_xml=subject.php

Physics

University of Exeter

Exeter, South West England

Waves and Optics is a compulsory module in year 1, Quantum Mechanics in year 2, and optional modules in year 3 and 4 include Quantum applications- Lasers and Quantum Optics and Photonics.

Contact : *+44 (0)1392 725349 – ug-ad-phys@exeter.ac.uk*

http://www.exeter.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/Physics/physicbsc

Physics and Astronomy

University of Glasgow

Glasgow, Scotland

Optics and Quantum Mechanics are taught through the degree, while years 3 and 4 offer modules in Laser physics and other modules related to photonics.

Contact : *Dr Morag Casey – (+44) 141 330 4709 – phas-ugadmissions@glasgow.ac.uk*

http://www.gla.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/Physics/#/programmestructure

Engineering Physics

Heriot Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

Photonics is studied in the second year, Optics in the third year along with Optical Processing and Laser Physics in the Fourth year.

Contact : *Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025 – physics@eps.hw.ac.uk*

http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/F314/

Physics with Energy Science and Technology

Heriot-Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

Photonics is studied in the second year, Optics in the third year along with Optical Processing and Laser Physics in the Fourth year.

Contact : *Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025 – physics@eps.hw.ac.uk*

http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/F390/

Nano-science

Heriot-Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

This degree contains material common to all the physics programs along with relevant biology and chemistry. Photonics, lasers and optics may be studied as options and as part of the course.

Contact : Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025– physics@eps.hw.ac.uk
<http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/CF10/>

Physics

Heriot-Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

Photonics is studied in the second year, Optics in the third year along with Optical Processing and Laser Physics in the Fourth year..

Contact : Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025– physics@eps.hw.ac.uk
<http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/F300/>

Physics

University of Hertfordshire

Hertfordshire, East of England

The first year includes Quantum Optics, Quantum Physics, Optical Physics and Contemporary Quantum Physics.

Contact : Dr Mark Thompson – M.A.Thompson@herts.ac.uk
<http://www.herts.ac.uk/courses/Physics>

Physics

University of Hull

Hull, Yorkshire and the Humber

Quantum Physics and Mechanics are studied in years 1, 2 and 3. Optical Communications and Photonic Devices are also available in year 3.

Contact : 0300 330 1504 – admissions@hull.ac.uk
<http://www2.hull.ac.uk/ug/courses/Physics.aspx>

Physics

Imperial College

London, Greater London

There are many Photonics related courses such as Quantum Physics and Mechanics, Optics, BioPhotonics and Lasers.

Contact : Dr Juliet Pickering – +44 (0)20 7594 7513 – ph.admissions@imperial.ac.uk
<http://www.imperial.ac.uk/study/ug/courses/Physics-department/Physics/>

Experimental Physics

National University of Ireland, Maynooth

Maynooth, Republic of Ireland

This degree covers the topics of Optics, Lasers and Quantum Mechanics.

Contact : +353 1 708 3641 – physics.department@nuim.ie
<https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/experimental-physics/physics>

Physics and Applied Physics (GY320)

National University of Ireland, Galway

Galway, Republic of Ireland

Optics & Quantum mechanics are offered in the third year of this course.

Contact : Tess Mahoney – +353 91 492490 – Tess.Mahoney@nuigalway.ie

http://www.nuigalway.ie/faculties_departments/physics/courses/denominated.html

Physics with Environmental Studies

Keele University

Staffordshir, Midlands

Quantum Mechanics and Optics & Thermodynamics modules are offered in the second year. Advanced Quantum Mechanics modules are offered in the third year.

Contact : 01782 734005 – admissions.ukeu@keele.ac.uk

<http://www.keele.ac.uk/ugcourses/physics/#tabs-1>

Physics

University of Kent

Canterbury, South East

This course offers Quantum Physics, Optics, Light and Relativity Optics.

Contact : +44 (0)1227 827272 – information@kent.ac.uk

<http://www.kent.ac.uk/courses/undergraduate/22/Physics-bsc#!structure>

Physics or Physics with Medical Application

King's College London

London, Greater London

Quantum Physics and Optics are both available to study at the King's College.

Contact : 020 7848 7517 – nms-ugadmissions@kcl.ac.uk

<http://www.kcl.ac.uk/prospectus/undergraduate/structure/name/physics>

Physics

University of Glasgow

Glasgow, Scotland

Optics and Quantum Physics are course modules in year 1 and are expanded on in year 2. Laser Physics is studied in year 3.

Contact : Dr Morag Casey – (+44) 141 330 5685 – phas-ugadmissions@glasgow.ac.uk

<http://www.gla.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/physics/>

Applied Physics

University of Central Lancashire

Central Lancashire, North West England

Quantum Physics in the second year and Quantum Mechanics in the third year.

Contact : 01772 830777 – uadmissions@uclan.ac.uk

http://www.uclan.ac.uk/courses/bsc_physics_foundation_entry.php

Physics

Lancaster University

Lancaster, North West England

Lasers and Applications, Quantum Mechanics and Quantum Physics and Optics are all included modules.

Contact : +44 (0)1524 592261 – enquiries@chester.ac.uk

<http://www.chester.ac.uk/undergraduate/natural-sciences>

Physics with Materials Science

University of Chester

Chester, North West England

Quantum Physics in year 1 with Quantum Mechanics in year 2.

Contact : Graham Smith – +44 (0) 124 451 1000 –

physics-ugadmissions@lancaster.ac.uk

<http://www.lancaster.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/physics-bsc-hons-f300/>

Physics

University of Leicester

Leicester, East Midlands

Waves and Quanta, Waves and Light and Quantum Mechanics are all studiable.

Contact : 0116 252 5281 – seadmissions@le.ac.uk

<http://www2.le.ac.uk/study/ugp/physics/physics>

Physics

University of Leeds

Leeds, North East

Quantum physics is taught in the first two years of this course, while in the third year you may opt to study advanced modules on Quantum optics and Photonics

Contact : +44 (0)113 343 3881 – physics.admissions@leeds.ac.uk

<http://www.physics.leeds.ac.uk/undergraduate/degree-courses/bsc-physics.html>

Applied Physics

University of Limerick

Limerick, Republic of Ireland

Optics is taught in the first two years of this course, and Quantum mechanics and optoelectronics is covered in the third and fourth years of study.

Contact : Dr Ian Clancy – 00 353 61 202015 – admissions@ul.ie

<http://www3.ul.ie/courses/AppliedPhysics.php>

Mathematics and Physics

University of Lincoln

Lincoln, East Midlands

Module included in the course are: Geometrical Optics, Quantum Physics and Quantum Mechanics.

Contact : 01522 886097 – admissions@lincoln.ac.uk

<http://www.lincoln.ac.uk/home/course/mthphyum/>

Physics

University of Lincoln

Lincoln, East Midlands

Module included in the course are: Geometrical Optics, Quantum Physics and Quantum Mechanics.

Contact : 01522 886097 – admissions@lincoln.ac.uk

<http://www.lincoln.ac.uk/home/course/mthphyum/>

Physics

University of Liverpool

Liverpool, North West England

Quantum Physics is covered in year two, of this course.

Contact : +44 (0)151 794 5927 – irro@liv.ac.uk

<http://www.liv.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/physics-bsc-hons/module-details/>

Physics for New Technology

University of Liverpool

Liverpool, North West England

Quantum Physics and Quantum Mechanics are both studied.

Contact : +44 (0)151 794 5927 – irro@liv.ac.uk

<https://www.liv.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/physics-for-new-technology-bsc-hons/overview/>

Physics

University College London

London, Greater London

Waves, Optics & Acoustics is a module in the first year, Quantum Mechanics is taught in the second and third years while you may opt to study a module on Lasers and modern optics in the third year.

Contact : Mrs Joanna Davies – +44 (0)20 7679 7246 – undergraduate-admissions@ucl.ac.uk

<http://www.ucl.ac.uk/prospective-students/undergraduate/degrees/physics-bsc/>

Physics

Loughborough University

Loughborough, Midlands

Quantum mechanics is taught in the second year, Modern optics is an optional module in the third year.

Contact : +44 (0)1509 228409 – physics.ug@lboro.ac.uk

<http://www.lboro.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/departments/physics/physics/>

Physics

University of Manchester

Manchester, North West

Quantum Mechanics is introduced and studied in the first and second years, while topics of study in the third year include electromagnetic radiation and lasers.

Contact : +44 (0)161 306 3673 – ug-physics@manchester.ac.uk

<http://www.physics.manchester.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/undergraduate-courses/physics-bsc/>

Applied Physics *The Manchester Metropolitan University*

Manchester, North West

Optics is taught in the first year, Quantum effects in the second year. There is the option of studying lasers, optics, and other photonics topics as part of the final year project.

Contact : +44 (0)161 247 6969 – direct@mmu.ac.uk

<http://www2.mmu.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/2016/13252/>

Physics *Newcastle University*

Newcastle, North East

Optics and Quantum Mechanics are both compulsory courses in the second year with advanced quantum mechanics in year three.

Contact : +44 (0) 191 208 3333

<http://www.ncl.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/f300/courseoverview/#d.en.139167>

Physics *Northumbria University*

Newcastle, North East

Optics and Quantum Mechanics are both compulsory courses in the second year with advanced quantum mechanics in year three.

Contact : +44 (0) 191 208 3333

<http://www.ncl.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/f300/courseoverview/#d.en.139167>

Mathematical Physics *The University of Nottingham*

Nottingham, East Midlands

Optics and Electromagnetism is a compulsory module in the second year, while several modules on Quantum Theory are studied in the third year of this course. Light & Matter and Quantum Coherent Phenomena are optional modules, available in the later years of this course.

Contact : Mrs Julie Kenney – +44 (0)115 951 5165 – julie.kenney@nottingham.ac.uk

<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/ugstudy/courses/physicsandastronomy/bsc-mathematical-physics.aspx>

Physics with Nanoscience *University of Nottingham*

Nottingham, East Midlands

This course follows the same syllabus as the BSc Physics programme with a focus on nanophysics modules. Optics and Electromagnetism is a compulsory module in the second year, while several modules on Quantum Theory are studied in the third year of this course. Light & Matter and Quantum Coherent Phenomena are optional modules, available in the later years of this course.

Contact : Mrs Julie Kenney – +44 (0)115 951 5165 – julie.kenney@nottingham.ac.uk

<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/ugstudy/courses/physicsandastronomy/bsc-physics-nanoscience.aspx>

Physics

University of Nottingham

Nottingham, East Midlands

Optics and Electromagnetism is a compulsory module in the second year, while several modules on Quantum Theory are studied in the third year of this course. Light & Matter and Quantum Coherent Phenomena are optional modules, available in the later years of this course.

Contact : Mrs Julie Kenney – +44 (0)115 951 5165 – julie.kenney@nottingham.ac.uk
<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/ugstudy/courses/physicsandastronomy/bsc-physics.aspx>

Physics

Nottingham Trent University

Nottingham, East Midlands

An Optics and Semiconductors module is taught in year two.

Contact : Edward Breeds – +44 (0)115 848 4200 – applications@ntu.ac.uk
[http://www.ntu.ac.uk/apps/pss/course_finder/118277-1/39/bsc_\(hons\)_physics.aspx?yoe=6&st=1&s=1&sv=PHYS&sl=1|2#course](http://www.ntu.ac.uk/apps/pss/course_finder/118277-1/39/bsc_(hons)_physics.aspx?yoe=6&st=1&s=1&sv=PHYS&sl=1|2#course)

Mathematics and Physics

The Open University

Milton Keynes, South East

This is a distance learning, mostly online, university for which you study off-campus. You may choose to study Quantum Physics, Quantum Mechanics and Optics.

Contact : +44 (0)1908 659253
<http://www.open.ac.uk/courses/qualifications/q77#course-details>

Physics

University of Oxford

Oxford, South East England

Optics, Quantum Physics and Quantum Mechanics are core modules spread out throughout the course.

Contact : +44 (0) 1865 272200 – enquiries@physics.ox.ac.uk
<http://www.ox.ac.uk/admissions/undergraduate/courses-listing/physics#>

Applied Physics

University of Portsmouth

Portsmouth, South East England

Waves and optics is taught in the second year of this course. In the third year, you have the option to choose to study Quantum mechanics with Application in Quantum Information and Nanostructures and Radiofrequency & Microwave physics.

Contact : +44 (0)23 9284 5550 – science.admissions@port.ac.uk
<http://www.port.ac.uk/courses/mathematics-and-physics/bsc-hons-applied-physics/>

Physics

Queen Mary University of London

London, Greater London

Quantum physics is covered in the first year of this course. Quantum Mechanics is covered in the second year, with the option of studying advanced Quantum Mechanics in the third year. There is a compulsory module on Electromagnetic waves and optics in the second year.

Contact : +44 (0)20 7882 5511 – admissions@qmul.ac.uk

<http://www.qmul.ac.uk/undergraduate/coursefinder/courses/79938.html>

Applied Mathematics and Physics

Queen's University Belfast

Belfast, Northern Ireland

Quantum theory is taught in year 3 of this programme, with advanced Quantum Theory in year 4.

Contact : +44 (0) 28 9097 6005 – mp@qub.ac.uk

<http://www.qub.ac.uk/home/StudyatQueens/CourseFinder/UG/MathematicalStudies/GF13/>

Physics

Queen's University Belfast

Belfast, Northern Ireland

Optics & Lasers and Quantum Theory are modules taught in the first year of this programme. In the second and third years, you will study Optics, electricity & Magnetism. You may also opt to study Electromagnetic Radiation & Modern Optics, Optoelectronics and Physical Electronics, and advanced modules in Quantum Mechanics in the third year.

Contact : +44 (0) 28 9097 6005 – mp@qub.ac.uk

<http://www.qub.ac.uk/home/StudyatQueens/CourseFinder/UG/Physics/F300/>

Environmental Physics

University of Reading

Reading

This course includes modules common to many physics degrees, with an emphasis on the applications of physics in environmental science. Optional modules include atmospheric spectroscopy in the third year.

Contact : +44 (0) 118 378 8372 – ugadmissions@reading.ac.uk

<http://www.reading.ac.uk/ready-to-study/study/subject-area/environment-ug/bsc-environmental-physics.aspx>

Physics

Royal Holloway University of London

London, Greater London

Optics and Quantum Mechanics may be studied in the second year of this course, with advanced Optics and Quantum Mechanics available in the third year.

Contact : Gill Green – +44 (0) 1784 443506 – Gill.Green@rhul.ac.uk

<https://www.royalholloway.ac.uk/physics/coursefinder/bscphysics.aspx>

Experimental Physics **Royal Holloway University of London**

London, Greater London

Optics and Quantum Mechanics may be studied in the second year of this course, with advanced Optics and Quantum Mechanics available in the third year.

Contact : Gill Green – +44 (0) 1784 443506 – Gill.Green@rhul.ac.uk

<https://www.royalholloway.ac.uk/physics/coursefinder/bscexperimentalphysics.aspx>

Pure and Applied Physics **University of Salford**

Manchester, North West

Electronics and Optoelectronics is a first year course in this programme. Introductory Optics and Quantum Mechanics are modules in the second year. Advanced Quantum Mechanics and Optics are third year modules.

Contact : +44 (0) 161 295 4545 – i.morrison@salford.ac.uk

<http://www.salford.ac.uk/ug-courses/pure-and-applied-physics>

Physics **University of Salford**

Manchester, North West

Electronics and Optoelectronics is a first year course in this programme. Introductory Optics and Quantum Mechanics are modules in the second year. Advanced Quantum Mechanics and Optics are third year modules.

Contact : +44 (0) 161 295 4545 – i.morrison@salford.ac.uk

<http://www.salford.ac.uk/ug-courses/physics2>

Physics **University of the West of Scotland**

Hamilton, Scotland

Optics and Quantum Mechanics are modules taught in the third and fourth years of this degree.

Contact : 0800 027 1000 – ask@uws.ac.uk

http://www.uws.ac.uk/special_3_years/physics/

Physics **University of Sheffield**

Sheffield, North East

Waves and Optics are first year modules. Quantum Physics and further Optics are modules in the second year of the degree. Atomic and Laser physics is a compulsory module in the third year.

Contact : +44 (0)114 222 4362 – physics.ucas@sheffield.ac.uk

<https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/prospectus/courseDetails.do?id=F3002015>

Physics

University of Southampton

Southampton, South East

Waves, light and Quanta and an introduction to photonics are first year modules. In the second year, photonics modules include several Quantum Physics modules and Practical Photonics. In the third year there are several photonics modules and you may select a photonics orientated BSc project.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 2969 – fpse-ugapply@soton.ac.uk

<http://www.phys.soton.ac.uk/programmes/f300-bsc-physics-3-yrs>

Physics with Quantum Technology

University of Surrey

Guildford, South East

Atoms and Quanta is a photonics module in the first year of this degree. In the second year, compulsory photonics modules are Electromagnetic waves, From Atoms to Lasers, Quantum Physics and light lab. In year three, you can study Light and Matter, Nanophotonics and a final project.

Contact : +44 (0)1483 681 681 – ug-enquiries@surrey.ac.uk

<http://www.surrey.ac.uk/undergraduate/physics-quantum-technologies>

Physics

University of St Andrews

St Andrews, Scotland

Quantum Mechanics modules are available throughout the degree. Optoelectronics and Nonlinear Optics, Laser Physics, Principles of optics are modules available in the second and third years of this degree. Many more photonics modules are available with the MPhys degree.

Contact : +44 (0)1334 46 2150 – physics@st-andrews.ac.uk

<http://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/courses/route/USHFPHYSPHY/year/2014-5>

Physics

University of Strathclyde

Glasgow, Scotland

Mechanics, Optics & Waves and Quantum Physics are studied in the first year, and built on in the second and third years. You will complete experiments related to photonics. In the fourth year, you may opt for an introduction to laser physics, laser optics and non-linear optics.

Contact : +44(0)1415483362 – study@phys.strath.ac.uk

<http://www.strath.ac.uk/courses/undergraduate/physics/>

Physics

University of Sussex

Brighton, South East

Oscillations, Waves & Optics is studied in the first year. Quantum Mechanics is taught in years two and three. There is the option of choosing a module on Lasers in the third year and advanced Quantum Mechanics.

Contact : +44 (0)1273 678557 – ug.admissions@physics.sussex.ac.uk

<http://www.sussex.ac.uk/study/ug/2015/1563/31104>

Physics with Nanotechnology

Swansea University

Swansea, Wales

Waves and Optics and The Quantum World are modules in the first year of the degree. Quantum Mechanics modules are continued throughout the degree. Many of the nanotechnology modules relate to or apply photonics.

Contact : 01792 295720 – physics-admissions@swansea.ac.uk

<http://www.swansea.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/science/physics/bsc-physics-and-nanotechnology-f390/#accept>

Physics

Trinity College Dublin

Dublin, Republic of Ireland

This degree covers experimental and theoretical aspects of Quantum Mechanics and Laser & Modern Optics.

Contact : +353 1 896 1675 – physics@tcd.ie

<https://www.tcd.ie/courses/undergraduate/az/course.php?id=DUBSC-PYSC-1SCI>

Physics

University of Warwick

Warwick, Midlands

Quantum Phenomena is a first year module. Electromagnetic theory and Optics and Quantum Mechanics and experiemntal physics are second year photonics related modules. In the third year, you may opt to choose the Optoelectronics module.

Contact : +44 (0)24 7652 3723 – ugadmissions@warwick.ac.uk

<http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/f300/>

Physics for Modern Technology
Waterford Institute of Technology

Waterford, Republic of Ireland

Electromagnetism and Physical Optics is a module available in the second year of this degree. In the third year, photonics related modules are Atomic, Quantum and Solid State device Physics, Physical Optics and Photonics. In year 4 there are modules in Advanced optics and Photonics Applications.

Contact : *Dr. Claire Keary – 051-834087 – ckeary@wit.ie*

Physics
University of York

York, North East

Quantum Physics is introduced in the first year. In the second year, you may study Application of Optics, Electromagnetism and Optics, and more Quantum Physics. In the third year there are modules on Nanotechnology, Quantum Computing, Optics and further Quantum Physics.

Contact : *Dr. Charles Barton – +44 (0)1904 322241 – physics-admissions@york.ac.uk*

MASTERS

Physics

Aberystwyth University

Aberystwyth, Wales

This course shares modules with the bachelors course at Aberystwyth, with modules in Optics, Optronics and Quantum Mechanics. In the fourth year, there is a core module on Quantum Technology. The Mphys project may be photonics related.

Contact : 01970 622021 – ug-admissions@aber.ac.uk

<https://courses.aber.ac.uk/undergraduate/mphys-physics-degree/>

Broadband and Optical Communications

Bangor University

Bangor, Wales

This is a postgraduate Masters course which includes taught modules on Broadband communication, mobile communication systems, data networks, RF and optical technologies and sensor systems. There is a research project for which you may choose a photonics related topic.

Contact : +44 (0)1248 382683 – eng-pg-admissions@bangor.ac.uk

<http://www.bangor.ac.uk/courses/postgraduate/broadband-and-optical-Communications-msc>

Physics

University of Bath

Bath, Southwest England

This integrated Mphys Physics course introduces Quantum Physics and Optics in year 1, Quantum & Atomic physics in year 2, Quantum Mechanics and Laser Physics in year 3 and Advanced Quantum Theory and photonics in year 4, along with a possibly photonics related MPhys project.

Contact : +44 (0)1225 38 6441 – ask-admissions@bath.ac.uk

<http://www.bath.ac.uk/catalogues/2011-2012/ph/USPH-AFM02.htm>

Physics

Queen's University Belfast

Belfast, Ireland

Optics and Lasers, Quantum Mechanics and Optoelectronics are covered by this course, with specialist modules in year 4 such as Atomic, Molecular & Optical Physics and Laser & Plasma Physics.

Contact : +44 (0) 28 9097 3838 – admissions@qub.ac.uk

<http://www.qub.ac.uk/home/StudyatQueens/CourseFinder/UG/Physics/F303/>

Physics

University of Birmingham

Birmingham, West Midlands

Optics, Quantum Mechanics, Optics, Experimental Physics, and several optional modules can be studied in the first 3 years. In the fourth year, the majority of the year is taken up by a research project, which can be photonics related.

Contact : +44 (0)121 414 4563 – physics-adms@bham.ac.uk

<http://www.birmingham.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/physics/physics-msci.aspx>

Physics

University of Bristol

Bristol, Southwest

Quantum mechanics is studied throughout this programme, with the addition of experimental physics in the first and second years. Optics is covered in the third year, while the fourth year is very flexible - you may choose photonics related modules.

Contact : +44 (0)117 394 1639 – sci-ug-admissions@bristol.ac.uk

<http://www.bristol.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/2016/physics/msci-physics/>

Natural Sciences

Cambridge University

Cambridge, UK

The natural sciences course is one of the broadest courses available in the world. You may choose physics and photonics courses throughout the programme. There is an optional fourth year, including several photonics options, which leads to an Msci degree.

Contact : (01223) 356454 – natsci@admin.cam.ac.uk

<http://www.natsci.tripos.cam.ac.uk/>

Condensed Matter and Photonics

Cardiff University

Cardiff, UK

This is a postgraduate course which has either the award of Mphil or PhD. You have the opportunity of choosing from a wide range of topics researched in the Condensed Matter and Photonics group.

Contact : Miss Nicola Hunt – +44 (0) 29 2087 6457 – physics-pg@cardiff.ac.uk

<http://courses.cardiff.ac.uk/postgraduate/course/detail/p338.html>

Physics

University of Dundee

Dundee, Scotland

You will study Light, Waves, Optics, Quantum Mechanics and Quantum properties of matter. There are advanced Quantum Mechanics, Photonics and Optics options if you choose the five year Msci degree.

Contact : +44 (0)1382 386968 – SSE@dundee.ac.uk

[http://www.dundee.ac.uk/study/ug/physics/?c=physics+\(msci\)](http://www.dundee.ac.uk/study/ug/physics/?c=physics+(msci))

Electronic Engineering and Physics

University of Dundee

Dundee, Scotland

You will study Light, Waves and Optics during the first 3 years of this programme. There are advanced Photonics and Optics options if you choose the 4 year MEng degree.

Contact : +44 (0)1382 386968 – SSE@dundee.ac.uk

<http://www.dundee.ac.uk/study/ug/physics/?c=electronic+engineering+&+physics>

Physics

Durham University

Durham, North East

Quantum Physics studied throughout the 4 year course, with option of studying advanced Quantum Physics, Atoms, Lasers and Qubits in year 4.

Contact : +44 (0)191 334 3726 – physics.admissions@durham.ac.uk

<https://www.dur.ac.uk/physics/undergraduate/courses/>

Chemical Physics with a Year in Industry

East Anglia University

Norwich, East of England

This 4 year course covers Quantum Mechanics, nanoparticles, laser systems and their applications, in addition to topics from physics, chemistry and mathematics. The third year consists of an industrial placement. In the fourth year, you will complete a research project.

Contact : +44 (0)1603 591515 – admissions@uea.ac.uk

<https://www.uea.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/degree/detail/mchem-chemical-physics-with-a-year-in-industry>

Physics

University of Edinburgh

Edinburgh, Scotland

Quantum Mechanics is taught in the third, fourth and fifth years. There are optional modules available in the fourth and fifth years on Lasers and their Applications.

Contact : Caroline Keir – +44 (0) 131 651 7855 – enquiries@ph.ed.ac.uk

<http://www.ph.ed.ac.uk/studying/undergraduate/our-degrees/physics>

Physics with a Year Abroad

University of Edinburgh

Edinburgh, Scotland

This degree shares a syllabus with the regular Mphys degree with Quantum Mechanics being taught in the third and fifth years. The fourth year is spent on a research project abroad. There is optional modules available in the fifth year on Lasers and their Applications.

Contact : Caroline Keir – +44 (0) 131 651 7855 – enquiries@ph.ed.ac.uk

<http://www.ph.ed.ac.uk/studying/undergraduate/our-degrees/physics-year-abroad>

Physics

University of Exeter

Exeter, South West England

Waves & Optics, Quantum Mechanics, Experimental Physics, Lasers, Materials & Nanoscale probes and Quantum Optics & Photonics are modules covered in this 4 year Mphys degree programme. You have the option of selecting a photonics related Mphys research project in year 4.

Contact : +44 (0)1392 725349 – ug-ad-phys@exeter.ac.uk

<http://www.exeter.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/physics/physicsmphys/>

Physics

University of Glasgow

Glasgow, Scotland

Optics and Quantum Physics are course modules in year 1 and are expanded on in year 2. Laser Physics is studied in year 3. The Msci degree further develops these topics and provides an opportunity to complete a photonics related research project.

Contact : *Dr Morag Casey – (+44) 141 330 4709 – phas-ugadmissions@glasgow.ac.uk
<http://www.gla.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/physics/#/programmestructure>*

Physics

University of Hertfordshire

Hertfordshire

This Mphys degree in physics is offered both as a postgraduate degree and as an integrated masters degree. Quantum Mechanics and Optics is covered in the first two years, and a placement is available in the third year. Photonics related research projects are offered in the final year.

Contact : *(01223) 356454 – natsci@admin.cam.ac.uk
<http://www.natsci.tripos.cam.ac.uk/>*

Condensed Matter and Photonics

Cardiff University

Cardiff, UK

This is a postgraduate course which has either the award of Mphil or PhD. You have the opportunity of choosing from a wide range of topics researched in the Condensed Matter and Photonics group.

Contact : *Dr Mark Thompson – +44 (0)1707 284605 – physics-admissions@herts.ac.uk
<http://www.herts.ac.uk/courses/physics3>*

Physics with Energy Science and Technology

Heriot-Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

Courses in Photonics, Quantum Mechanics, Optics, Laser Physics, Optical Metrology and Applications of Lasers are covered through this degree after the first year.

Contact : *Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025 – physics@eps.hw.ac.uk
<http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/F391/>*

Chemical Physics

Heriot Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

Courses in Photonics, Quantum Mechanics, Optics, Laser Physics, Optical Metrology and Applications of Lasers are covered through this degree, and advanced in the fifth year.

Contact : *Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025 – physics@eps.hw.ac.uk
<http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/F322/>*

Photonics and Optoelectronic Devices

Heriot Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

This is a postgraduate MSc degree which delivers training in modern optics and semiconductor physics tailored to optoelectronic applications. You will gain knowledge about optical fibres and the technology and applications of optical communication.

Contact : Prof A K Kar – +44 (0) 131 451 3049 – A.K.Kar@hw.ac.uk

<http://www.postgraduate.hw.ac.uk/prog/msc-photonics-and-optoelectronic-devices/>

Nano-science

Heriot Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

This is an integrated Mphys degree containing material common to the physics programme, such as optics and Quantum Mechanics. The fifth year is half dedicated to teaching material on nano-scale topics in Physics, Chemistry and Photonics.

Contact : Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025 – physics@eps.hw.ac.uk

<http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/FC01/>

Physics

Heriot Watt University

Edinburgh, Scotland

Some of the core concepts of this 5 year integrated Mphys course are Optics, Lasers and Photonics. The fifth year is taken up by a research project.

Contact : Patrik Ohberg – +44 (0)131 451 3025 – physics@eps.hw.ac.uk

<http://www.undergraduate.hw.ac.uk/programmes/F302/>

Physics

University of Hertfordshire

Hertfordshire, East of England

Quantum Mechanics, Optical Physics & Electromagnetism are covered through this course, with a professional placement in the third year as a sandwich year.

Contact : +44 (0) 1707 284800 – ask@herts.ac.uk

<http://www.herts.ac.uk/courses/physics3>

Optics and Photonics

Imperial College

London, Greater London

Fibre technology, Laser Optics, Optics, Photonics structure, Optoelectronics, Laser Technology and Optical Design are all available modules in this postgraduate MSc degree.

Contact : 01603 591515 – I.sanchez@imperial.ac.uk

<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/study/pg/physics/optics-photonics/>

Physics

Imperial College

London, Greater London

There are many Photonics related courses such as Quantum Physics and Mechanics, Optics, BioPhotonics and Laser Technology. Quantum Optics is also available.

Contact : *Dr Juliet Pickering – +44 (0)20 7594 7513 – ph.admissions@imperial.ac.uk
<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/study/ug/courses/physics-department/physics/>*

Physics

University of Hull

Hull, North East

This Mphys degree covers a range of topic in modern physics, including Quantum Mechanics and Optics. There are options to specialise in photonics related topics through optional modules the the final year research project.

Contact : *+44(0)1482465231 – admissions-physics@hull.ac.uk
<http://www2.hull.ac.uk/ug/courses/physics-mphys.aspx>*

Physics

University of Kent

Canterbury, South East

This course offers Quantum Physics, Optics, Light Relativity Optics and Modern Optics.

Contact : *+44 (0)1392 725349 – phas-ugadmissions@glasgow.ac.uk
<http://www.gla.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/Physics/#/programmestructure>*

Physics

University of Leeds

Leeds, North East

In the first few years of this integrated Mphys degree, you will follow the Bsc course, studying Quantum Physics, Waves, Optics. Later in the degree, you may study modules and projects linked closely to current research, including Quantum Optics & Photonics.

Contact : *+44 (0)113 343 3881 – physics.admissions@leeds.ac.uk
<http://www.physics.leeds.ac.uk/undergraduate/degree-courses/mphys-bsc-physics.html>*

Physics

King's College London

London, Greater London

King's college offers courses in Spectroscopy, Quantum Mechanics and Optics in the first 3 years. In the fourth year, there is the option to study Photon Physics and Advanced Quantum mechanics, along with a research project.

Contact : *020 7848 7517 – nms-ugadmissions@kcl.ac.uk
https://www.kcl.ac.uk/prospectus/undergraduate/index/name/physics-msci/alpha/PQR/header_search//from/searchall/keyword/physics*

Mathematics and Physics

King's College London

London, Greater London

Similar to the BSc and Msci Physics programmes, this course gives you the opportunity to study Quantum mechanics, Optics and Spectroscopy. In the fourth year, there are modules on advanced Quantum Mechanics and Photonics, along with the research project.

Contact : 020 7848 7517 – nms-ugadmissions@kcl.ac.uk

https://www.kcl.ac.uk/prospectus/undergraduate/index/name/mathematics-and-physics-msci/alpha/PQR/header_search//from/searchall/keyword/physics

Applied Physics

University of Central Lancashire

Preston, North West England

This Mphys programme is focussed on the applications of physics - there are modules on Waves, Quantum Mechanics, Experimental Physics and Lasers & Modern Optics. In addition, there is a research project and advanced laboratory work in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)1772 892400 – cenquiries@uclan.ac.uk

http://www.uclan.ac.uk/courses/mphys_applied_physics.php

Physics

University of Central Lancashire

Preston, North West England

Quantum Mechanics and Optics are covered in the first 3 years. Lasers and modern Optics is an optional fourth year course. There is a compulsory research project in the fourth year, which could be centered on photonics.

Contact : +44 (0)131 451 3025 – cenquiries@uclan.ac.uk

http://www.uclan.ac.uk/courses/mphys_physics.php

Physics

Lancaster University

Lancaster, North West England

Optics and Optical Instruments, Quantum Mechanics, Waves, Lasers and Quantum Information Processing may all be studied as part of this Mphys degree in physics. There is a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)1524 592261 – physics-ugadmissions@lancaster.ac.uk

http://www.physics.lancs.ac.uk/study_here/undergraduate/courses/Physics-MPhys-Hons

Physics

University of Leicester

Leicester, East Midlands

This 4 year Mphys programme covers Optics, Quantum Mechanics, Waves and Quanta and Light & Matter. There is a compulsory research project in the final year, for which you may choose a Photonics Related topic.

Contact : +44 (0)116 252 5281 – seadmissions@le.ac.uk

https://le.ac.uk/courses/physics-mphys?uol_r=0d9f63eb

Physics with Nanotechnology University of Leicester

Leicester, East midlands

This degree follows the same core modules as the regular MPhys degree. Topics that can be studied include Light and Matter, Waves and Quanta, Quantum Devices, Quantum Mechanics and additional modules relating to Nanotechnology. There is a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)116 252 5281 – seadmissions@le.ac.uk

https://le.ac.uk/courses/physics-with-nanotechnology-mphys?uol_r=0992f1d3

Mathematics and Physics University of Lincoln

Lincoln, East Midlands

This Mathematics and Physics MMath degree teaches modules such as Geometrical Optics, waves, Quantum Mechanics and Nano-Physics, along with mathematics modules. There is a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)1522 886644

<http://www.lincoln.ac.uk/home/course/mthphyum/>

Physics University of Lincoln

Lincoln, East Midlands

This MPhys Physics degree includes modules on Quantum physics, Geometrical Optics, Waves, Experimental Physics, Nano-Physics and a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)1522 886644

<http://www.lincoln.ac.uk/home/course/phyphyum/>

Physics Loughborough University

Loughborough, East Midlands

This MPhys Physics course includes modules on Modern Optics, Quantum Mechanics and Quantum Physics, with a final year research project.

Contact : +44 (0)1509 228409 – physics.ug@lboro.ac.uk

<http://www.lboro.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/departments/physics/physics/>

Physics University of Manchester

Manchester, North West

This MPhys physics degree includes units on waves, Quantum mechanics and lasers, with a compulsory final year project.

Contact : +44 (0)161 306 3673 – ug-physics@manchester.ac.uk

<http://www.physics.manchester.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/undergraduate-courses/physics-mphys/>

Physics

Newcastle University

Newcastle, North East

Optics and Quantum Mechanics are both compulsory courses whilst Photonics is an optional 4th year course in this 4 year MPhys degree.

Contact : +44 (0) 191 208 3333 – uadmissions@uclan.ac.uk

<http://www.ncl.ac.uk/undergraduate/degrees/f303/courseoverview/>

Physics

Northumbria University

Newcastle, North East

Quantum Mechanics are studied in years 2 and 4 with optoelectronic devices being studied in year 4. Optical Communication is another available year 4 course.

Contact : 0191 349 5600 – course.enquiries@northumbria.ac.uk

<https://www.northumbria.ac.uk/study-at-northumbria/courses/physics-mphys-ft-uusimy1/>

Photonic and Optical Engineering

University of Nottingham

Nottingham, Midlands

This is a 1 year MSc degree with taught modules on Photonics and Optical Engineering, as well as a research project.

Contact : +44 (0) 115 951 5559 – postgraduate-enquiries@nottingham.ac.uk

<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/pgstudy/courses/electrical-and-electronic-engineering/photonic-and-optical-engineering-msc.aspx>

Physics

University of Nottingham

Nottingham, Midlands

This 4 year MPhys degree includes modules on Quantum Mechanics, Atoms & Photons, Light & Matter and Coherent Phenomena. There is a research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0) 115 951 5165 – julie.kenney@nottingham.ac.uk

<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/ugstudy/courses/physicsandastronomy/msci-physics.aspx>

Physics with Nanoscience

University of Nottingham

Nottingham, Midlands

This is a specialised MPhys degree in Physics with Nanotechnology shares modules such as Quantum Mechanics, Atoms & Photons, Light & Matter and Coherent Phenomena with the MPhys Physics degree, with additional compulsory Nanotechnology modules and projects.

Contact : +44 (0) 115 951 5165 – julie.kenney@nottingham.ac.uk

<http://www.nottingham.ac.uk/ugstudy/courses/physicsandastronomy/msci-physics-nanoscience.aspx>

Physics

Nottingham Trent University

Nottingham, Midlands

Photonics modules in this 4 year MSci degree include medical imaging, Quantum Mechanics and Optics. There is a compulsory final year research project.

Contact : +44 (0)115 848 4200 – applications@ntu.ac.uk

http://www.ntu.ac.uk/apps/pss/course_finder/76094-1/9/msci_physics.aspx

Physics

University of Oxford

Oxford, South East England

This course contains modules on Optics, Quantum mechanics, Experimental Physics, Laser Science and Quantum Information Processing. There is a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0) 1865 272200 – enquiries@physics.ox.ac.uk

<http://www.ox.ac.uk/admissions/undergraduate/courses-listing/physics>

Applied Physics

University of Portsmouth

Portsmouth, South East England

This course teaches Waves and Optics, Quantum Mechanics, Experimental Physics, Quantum Information. There is a compulsory final year research project.

Contact : +44 (0)23 9284 5550 – science.admissions@port.ac.uk

<http://www.port.ac.uk/courses/mathematics-and-physics/mphys-hons-applied-physics/>

Physics, Astronomy and Cosmology.

University of Portsmouth

Portsmouth, South East England

Waves and Optics and Quantum Mechanics are modules that are taught as part of this MPhys degree, with a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)23 9284 5550 – science.admissions@port.ac.uk

<http://www.port.ac.uk/courses/mathematics-and-physics/mphys-hons-physics-astronomy-and-cosmology/>

Physics

Queen Mary University of London

London, Greater London

You may Study Optics, Quantum Physics, Quantum Mechanics and Photon Physics in this 4 year MSci course. There is a compulsory research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)20 7882 6958 – physics@qmul.ac.uk

<http://www.qmul.ac.uk/undergraduate/coursefinder/courses/79936.html>

Physics

Queen's University Belfast

Belfast, Northern Ireland

Optics and Lasers, Quantum Mechanics and Optoelectronics are covered by this course, with specialist modules in year 4 such as Atomic, Molecular & Optical Physics and Laser & Plasma Physics and a research project.

Contact : +44 (0) 28 9097 6005 – mp@qub.ac.uk

<http://www.qub.ac.uk/home/StudyatQueens/CourseFinder/UG/Physics/F303/>

Experimental Physics

Royal Holloway, University of London

Egham, South East

This masters course in Experimental Physics covers all of the core skills and concepts of a Physics degree in the first two years but provide an additional focus on the experimental techniques and methods. The fourth year has options including Quantum Computation, Nanoscale Physics and others.

Contact : Gill Green – +44 (0) 1784 443506 – Gill.Green@rhul.ac.uk

<https://www.royalholloway.ac.uk/physics/coursefinder/msciexperimentalphysics.aspx>

Physics

Royal Holloway, University of London

Egham, South East

In this MSci degree, you will have the opportunity to learn about Quantum Mechanics, Optics , Experimental Physics, Waves, Optics, Photon physics, Advanced Photonics and Quantum Computing. You will undertake a 6 month major project in the final year.

Contact : Gill Green – +44 (0) 1784 443506 – Gill.Green@rhul.ac.uk

<https://www.royalholloway.ac.uk/physics/coursefinder/msciphysics.aspx>

Physics

University of Salford

Manchester, North West

Photonics related modules that may be studied as part of this MPhys degree are Optoelectronics, Optics and Quantum Mechanics, with a research project in the final year.

Contact : 0161 295 3306 – ug-admissions@salford.ac.uk

<http://www.salford.ac.uk/ug-courses/physics>

Semiconductor Photonics and Electronics

University of Sheffield

Sheffield, UK

This is a 1 year postgraduate MSc course which focuses on Semiconductor Materials, Semiconductor Device Technology, Microsystems, Nanoscale Devices, Optical Communication and Semiconductor Manufacturing. There is also a major research project.

Contact : +44 (0)114 222 5442 – n.porter@sheffield.ac.uk

<http://www.sheffield.ac.uk/postgraduate/taught/courses/engineering/electronic/semiconductor>

Physics

University of Sheffield

Sheffield, UK

This 4 year integrated Masters course includes modules on Qaves, Optics, Quantum Mechanics, Atomic & Laser physics and the Optical Properties of Solids. Ther is a compulsory research project in the fourth year.

Contact : 0114 222 4362 – physics.ucas@sheffield.ac.uk

<http://www.sheffield.ac.uk/physics/undergraduate-admissions/courses/physics>

Physics with Photonics

University of Southampton

Southampton, South East

This is one of the only dedicated integrated Photonics masters degrees in the UK. Students will cover the same core as a physics degree, but will specialise in experimental and prtactical photonics, light and matter, lasers and a huge range of very specialised modules and project in the fourth year.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 2969 – fpse-ugapply@soton.ac.uk

<http://www.phys.soton.ac.uk/programmes/f369-mphys-physics-photonics-4-yrs>

Experimental Physics Final Year Research

University of Southampton

Southampton, South East

This degree follows the same core modules as a regular physics degree, but gives the opportunity for students to spend their final year entirely on a research project. There are options all through the degree to take both generalized and specialized photonics modules.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 2969 – fpse-ugapply@soton.ac.uk

<http://www.phys.soton.ac.uk/programmes/f303-mphys-physics-year-experimental-research-4-yrs>

Physics with Nanotechnology

University of Southampton

Southampton, South East

This degree follows the same core modules as a regular physics degree, but requires that students take a set list of nanotechnology modules. Theses include some photonics modules, and there is the option to take more.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 2969 – fpse-ugapply@soton.ac.uk

<http://www.phys.soton.ac.uk/programmes/f390-mphys-physics-nanotechnology>

Photonics, Optoelectronics, Lasers and Fibre Optics

University of St Andrews

Fife, Scotland

This 1 year course provides postgraduate vocational training in lasers, modern optics and semiconductors, tailored to the needs of the optoelectronics, lasers, photonics, and optical communications industry. There is a 3.5 month research project which is usually in industry.

Contact : 01334 463103 – physics@st-and.ac.uk

https://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/physics/prosp_pg/opto_msc/newmsc.php

Optical Technologies University of Strathclyde

Glasgow, UK

This 1 year postgraduate masters degree teaches topics such as Lasers, Nonlinear Optics, Optics, Ultrafast Physics & Plasmas, Photonics Materials and more. There is a research project that runs throughout the year.

Contact : +44 (0) 1415483362 – pgt@phys.strath.ac.uk

<https://www.strath.ac.uk/courses/postgraduatetaught/opticaltechnologies/>

Physics University of Surrey

Guildford, South East

This is a 4 year integrated masters degree, which covers general physics topics in addition to Quantum Mechanics, Optics, Nonlinear Physics, Lasers and Advances in Photonics. There is the option to do a year in professional placement. There is a research project in the final year.

Contact : Dr Annika Lohstroh – +44 (0)1483 681 681 – admissions@surrey.ac.uk

<http://www.surrey.ac.uk/undergraduate/physics>

Physics with Quantum Technology University of Surrey

Guildford, South East

This course covers Waves, Quantum Mechanics, Light, Lasers and Nanophotonics. There is a placement in industry or academia and a research project in year 3 or 4.

Contact : +44 (0)1483 681 681 – admissions@surrey.ac.uk

<http://www.surrey.ac.uk/undergraduate/physics-quantum-technologies>

Frontiers of Quantum Technology University of Sussex

Brighton, South East

This 1 year MSc degree studies Quantum Phenomena; quantum teleportation, quantum cryptography, and quantum computing. There is a research project which makes up 50% of this course, with lectures making up the other half.

Contact : Student Recruitment Services – +44 (0)1273 678557 – msc@physics.sussex.ac.uk

www.sussex.ac.uk/study/pg/2016/taught/1670/33383#subject

Physics University of Sussex

Brighton, South East

This is a 1 year postgraduate MSc degree with taught courses on Quantum Circuits, Quantum Technology, Fibre-Optics, Quantum Mechanics, Lasers and more. There is a research project which composes the other half of this degree.

Contact : Student Recruitment Services – +44 (0)1273 678557 – msc@physics.sussex.ac.uk

www.sussex.ac.uk/study/pg/2016/taught/1670/33383#subject

Physics (research placement)

University of Sussex

Brighton, South East

This is a 4 year integrated Mphys degree, which is composed of a normal physics degree, in which you will learn topics such as Quantum Mechanics, Optics, Lasers and Nanotechnology, with the addition of a year in one of the Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics research groups.

Contact : +44 (0)1273 678557 – ug.admissions@physics.sussex.ac.uk

<http://www.sussex.ac.uk/physics/ugstudy/researchplacement>

Physics

Swansea University

Swansea, Wales

This is a 4 year integrated Mphys degree, which will teach Waves and Optics, Experimental Physics, Quantum Mechanics, Quantum Optics and Lasers.

Contact : 01792 295720 – physics-admissions@swansea.ac.uk

<http://www.swansea.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/science/physics/mphys-physics-f303/>

Physics with a Year Abroad

Swansea University

Swansea, Wales

This is a 4 year integrated Mphys degree, which will teach Waves and Optics, Experimental Physics, Quantum Mechanics, Quantum Optics and Lasers. This includes a year studying abroad.

Contact : 01792 295720 – physics-admissions@swansea.ac.uk

<http://www.swansea.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/science/physics/mphys-physics-with-a-year-abroad-f304/>

Physics

University of Warwick

Warwick, Midlands

This 4 year integrated Mphys course teaches topics such as Quantum Mechanics, Experimental physics and Optics. There is a research project in the final year.

Contact : +44 (0)24 7652 3723 – ugadmissions@warwick.ac.uk

<http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/study/undergraduate/courses/f303/>

Physics

University of York

York, North East

This is a 4 year integrated Mphys degree, with modules on Waves, Optics, Quantum Physics, Applications of Optics and Lasers, with a research project in the final year. There is an option to study abroad or to spend a year in industry.

Contact : +44 (0)1904 322241 – physics-admissions@york.ac.uk

<https://www.york.ac.uk/physics/undergraduate/degree-courses/mphys-physics/>

DOCTORAL

Electronic Engineering and Physics (MSc by research) **University of Dundee**

Dundee, Scotland

The Division of Electronic Engineering, Physics & Renewable Energy: renewable energy, nanotechnology, bio-medical physics, optical manipulation and photonics.

Contact : *Linda Rannie*

Aston Institute of Photonic Technologies **Aston University**

Birmingham, Midlands

The Aston Institute of Photonic Technologies offers PhD studentships in Optical Communication, Nonlinear photonics, Optical sensing, Femtosecond Lasers, Fibre Lasers, Biomedical photonics and Optoelectronics, subject to availability.

Contact : *+44 (0)121 204 3000 – photonics@aston.ac.uk*

<http://www.aston.ac.uk/eas/research/groups/photonics/postgraduate-opportunities/>

Centre for Photonics and Photonic Materials **University of Bath**

Bath, Midlands

The University of Bath offers PhD studentships in photonics in the Centre for Photonics and Photonic Materials. Current research topics include photonic crystal fibres, hollow-core and multi-core fibre designs, wavelength conversion, high power pulsed laser delivery, endoscopy and fibre lasers.

Contact : *Dr William Wadsworth – +44 (0) 1225 386946 – W.J.Wadsworth@bath.ac.uk*

<http://www.bath.ac.uk/research/centres/cppm/join-us/potential-supervisors.html>

Centre for Quantum Photonics **University of Bristol**

Bristol, West Midlands

The Centre for Quantum Photonics offers research PhD studentships in Quantum Communications, Quantum Sensing and Quantum Computing, subject to availability.

Contact : *+44 (0)117 928 9000 – cqp-enquiries@bristol.ac.uk*

<http://www.bristol.ac.uk/physics/research/quantum/opportunities/>

Photonics **University of Bristol**

Bristol, West Midlands

The Photonics group in the Faculty of Engineering provides research photonics PhD studentships in a variety of areas, subject to availability.

Contact : *+44 (0)117 928 9000 – pg-admissions@bristol.ac.uk*

<http://www.bristol.ac.uk/study/postgraduate/2016/eng/pg-r-listing/index.html>

Photonics **University of Cambridge**

Cambridge, East Anglia

The university of Cambridge offers PhD studentships in 3 research groups, with topics including photonic materials, communications and sensing, and photonic devices and applications. Subject to availability.

Contact : +44 (0)1223 760606 – Graduate.Admissions@admin.cam.ac.uk
<http://www-g.eng.cam.ac.uk/photonics/>

Condensed Matter and Photonics Group **University of Cardiff**

Cardiff, Wales

Cardiff University offers PhD studentships in the Condensed Matter and Photonics Group, which studies Photonics & Biophotonics, Quantum Materials & Devices, Nanoscale Science & Technology, Theory & Computational Physics and Imaging, Sensors & Instrumentation.

Contact : +44 (0)29 208 70084 – postgradenquiries@cardiff.ac.uk
<http://www.astro.cardiff.ac.uk/degreeprogrammes/pg/?page=physics>

EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Photonic Integration and Advanced Data Storage **University of Cardiff**

Glasgow, Scotland

The Centre's focus is on developing highly-manufacturable photonic integration technologies related to the magnetic storage of digital information. It provides PhD studentships depending on availability.

Contact : piads.cdt@qub.ac.uk
<http://www.gla.ac.uk/schools/engineering/research/centrefordoctoraltraining/#tabs=3>

Institute of Photonics and Quantum Sciences **Heriot Watt University**

Edinburgh, Scotland

The Institute of Photonics and Quantum Sciences spans research including lasers and optical sensing approaches, manufacturing methods and quantum information. There will be a special focus on quantum sciences and its close relationship with photonics-based technology.

Contact : Prof Ajoy Kay – +44 (0) 131 451 3049 – A.K.K@hw.ac.uk
<http://www.hw.ac.uk/schools/engineering-physical-sciences/research/phd/physics.htm>

Photonics **Imperial College**

London, Greater London

The Photonics group at Imperial College London offer PhD studentships in Biophotonics, Laser Physics, Electromagnetic Theory, Nonlinear Fibre Optics, Imaging and Sensing, subject to availability.

Contact : +44 (0)20 7589 5111 – m.salviato@imperial.ac.uk

http://www3.imperial.ac.uk/photonics/pg_opportunities/phd_opportunities

Photonics **University College London**

London, Greater London

The Photonics Group is involved in studies of opto-electronic devices, sub-systems and systems ranging from semiconductor lasers and liquid crystal wavelength division multiplex filters to millimetre-wave over fibre broadband access systems. They offer PhD studentships subject to availability.

Contact : Dr Ioannis Papakonstantinou – +44 (0)20 7679 7302 – phdenquiries@ee.ucl.ac.uk

<https://www.ee.ucl.ac.uk/doctorate/programme>

Institute of Microwaves and Photonics **University of Leeds**

Leeds, North East

The University of Leeds offers PhD studentships in Terahertz, Nanotechnology, Bionanoelectronics and Quantum Electronics where available.

Contact : +44 (0)113 343 8000 – phd@engineering.leeds.ac.uk

<http://www.engineering.leeds.ac.uk/electronic/postgraduate/research-degrees/index.shtml>

Photonics Engineering and Health Technology Group **Loughborough University**

Loughborough, Midlands

Loughborough University offers PhD studentships in the Photonics Engineering and Health Technology Research Group. Research areas include Biomedical Photonics, Imaging Processing and Health Technology.

Contact : Julie Allen – +44 (0)1509 227087 – j.d.allen@lboro.ac.uk

<http://www.lboro.ac.uk/departments/eese/pg-research/>

Photonics **University of Manchester**

Manchester, North West

Phd studentships in physics are offered at the University of Manchester subject to availability. Key research areas in the photon physics group are low energy lighting, solar cells, medical and biological uses of lasers and fundamental atomic and molecular physics.

Contact : +44 (0)161 306 3673 – pg-physics@manchester.ac.uk
<http://www.physics.manchester.ac.uk/our-research/divisions/condensed-matter-atomic-and-biological-physics/photon-physics/postgraduatestudy/>

Photonics **University of Oxford**

Oxford, Midlands

The University of Oxford offers PhD studentships in physics, where research areas in photonics include Devices, Imaging, Optics, Spectroscopy and Biophotonics where available.

Contact : +44 (0)1865 272200 – PGAdmissions@physics.ox.ac.uk
<https://www2.physics.ox.ac.uk/study-here/postgraduates>

Quantum, Light and Matter **University of Southampton**

Southampton, South East

The Quantum, Light and Matter group at the University of Southampton provide PhD studentships in Nanophotonics, Optical Materials, integrated atom chips & Quantum Control, Nanocrystals, Quantum Theory, Lasers and Terahertz, subject to availability.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 2093 – ceris@phys.soton.ac.uk
<http://www.qim.soton.ac.uk/join>

Optoelectronics Research Centre **University of Southampton**

Southampton, South East

The Optoelectronic Research Centre provides over 30 PhD studentships in a wide variety of photonics applications.

Contact : +44 (0)23 8059 3144 – fpse-phdapply@soton.ac.uk
<http://www.orc.soton.ac.uk/phdprogram.html>

Photonics **University of St Andrews**

Fife, Scotland

The university of St Andrews offers PhD studentships in Laser Physics, Biophotonics, Nanotechnology, Optoelectronics, Quantum optics and Millimetre and Terahertz technology. Subject to availability.

Contact : +(01334) 463111 – physics@st-andrews.ac.uk

http://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/physics/prosp_pg/phd/current_phd_projects.php?theme=5&filter=3

Institute of Photonics **University of Strathclyde**

Edinburgh, Scotland

The University of Strathclyde offers PhD studentships subject to availability in research areas such as Photonic materials and devices, Neurophotonics and Lasers.

Contact : 0141 548 4120 – iop@strath.ac.uk

<http://www.strath.ac.uk/photronics/phdandmscplaces/>

Photonics **University of Surrey**

Guildford, South East

The Photonics group at the University of Surrey offers PhD studentships where available in research areas such as quantum superposition of electron orbits in phosphorous doped silicon, development of new III-V materials and technologies, and development of efficient photovoltaics for laser power transfer applications.

Contact : +44 (0)1483 686 128 – gradschoolfeps@surrey.ac.uk

<http://www.surrey.ac.uk/postgraduate/physics-phd>

Photonics **University of York**

York, North East

The aim of the photonics group at York is to design and fabricate photonic crystals and other wavelength-scale structures that manipulate the flow of light. The group's activities span the study of nanostructured silicon photonics, biophotonics, and photovoltaics. They offer PhD studentships subject to demand.

Contact : Dr Yvette Hancock – +44 (0)1904 322204 – y.hancock@york.ac.uk

<https://www.york.ac.uk/physics/postgraduate/researchprojects/>

Photonics4All is a European Horizon 2020 Outreach project, funded by the European Commission to promote photonics and light based technologies to young people, entrepreneurs and the general public across the EU. Photonics4all's unique selling point is that it will both develop a set of new promotional tools and apply them during a wide variety of outreach activities with different audiences.

*Discover our unique approach and check out our tools and events :
<http://photonics4all.eu/>.*

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

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